

A simple long term storage solution for human tissues as source of continuous DNA / RNA for PCR analysis

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Abstract: In molecular biology, there is a need of storage solution of tissue for long term analysis in order to have a suitable source of nucleic acid (RNA and DNA). There are many reports to store the tissue and samples in different solutions like ethanol, DMSO along with storage in liquid nitrogen, but a suitable storage solution for tissue at room temperature for years is missing. Therefore, a solution called Genekam Tissue Storage Solution (GTSS) is developed. Human tissues were stored in this solution for 4 years., which are tested successfully with real time PCR after isolation of RNA and DNA over period of 4 years along with spectrometric testing.

Conclusion: In this work, it may be first time about a successful development of a simple long-term noncryogenic storage solution for human tissues at room temperature as continuous source of DNA and RNA for molecular biological analysis.

Keywords: Tissue storage solution, PCR, Tissue, Nucleic acid isolation

Introduction: Molecular biological methods like polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for detection and expression of different gene targets are part and parcel of modern medicine. (Bhatia 2021) Nucleic acid isolation is an essential step to conduct these studies.

During the PCR analysis, one uses different carriers like buccal swabs to isolate the DNA / RNA from nasal as well as mouth cavity for conducting various molecular biological testing e.g., detecting of human RNA viruses. (Lee et al. 2009, Bhatia, 2023) These buccal swabs can be stored for many days at room temperature and in cooling conditions. Moreover, these can be sent to other laboratories with the postal services at other destination. The problem arises, when it comes to store the tissue for long-term use as there is no standardized method available and degradation of nucleic acid in the tissue put a lot of pressure on the laboratories to conduct the studies as early as possible, therefore scientific community is searching for a suitable solution to store the tissue for long-term applications. There are reports that one can store the tissues at -20 OC also, which is not feasible under field conditions and there are costs of power supply. (Straube and Juen, 2013) There are many reports that one can store the tissues in DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) solutions as well as ethanol. (Kilpatrick 2002, Allen-Hall and McNevin 2013, Mirsha et al 2019). The biobanks need a solution to store the tissues and they used many different commercial solutions to solve the storage issue, but found that the storage at room temperature is possible for a few hours during the quality assessment studies. (Mutter et al. 2004, Lindner et al. 2019) Freezing temperatures are being used to store the tissues to maintain the integrity of nucleic acid as well as a report about doing the comparison of storage of tumor tissues at -80 OC or in liquid nitrogen in order to have constant supplier of DNA and RNA for studying the gene expression as well as gene sequencing in cancer tissue biobank. (Botling, 2009, Babel et al. 2020) In reality the liquid nitrogen can not be used for transportation the tissues.

Therefore, our laboratory decided to develop an inexpensive noncryogenic solutions for long-term storage of human tissues for different molecular biological applications.

Methods: Ethical committee of the institute gave permission for conducting the studies. A solution containing different chemicals are created with a particular PH. The composition of this solution can not be disclosed as patent rights are being assessed. This is available under the brand name: Genekam Tissue storage solution (GTSS).

Placenta and umbilical cord were donated and donor gave the consent to use these for scientific purposes. Both were stored at 4 °C for 2 weeks. After that a part of these samples were cut in small pieces of 3 mm each and put in 20 ml of GTSS in two 50 ml plastic tubes . They were stored over 4 years at room temperature.

During storage period, the RNA and DNA were isolated with mini column nucleic acid isolation kits (Genekam, Germany). If GTSS in tissue were reduced, extra 5 ml of GTSS were added. 100 ul from stored tissue solution was used as input and protocol was followed as per manufacturer and discussed in previous research work. The eluted volume of 50 to 100 ul per isolation was achieved. (Bhatia 2021)

The presence of human housekeeping genes like beta actin and beta globin in isolated RNA and DNA samples were done with real time PCR tests (Genekam Kit number FR799 and FR199) in ABI 7500 and Quantstudion 5 (Thermofischer, USA). (Bhatia 2021) 2ul of isolated nucleic acid was used as input for conducting the PCR testing. They were also conducted according to instructions of ready to use PCR kits from Genekam, Germany. The procedures are available as manuals from Genekam.

The conventional PCR was performed with internal control PCR kits (Genekam, Germany) and the bands were observed in the gel agarose. The instructions are available as manual from the manufacturer.

Spectrometric analysis of isolated RNA and DNA were done on Nanodrop (Thermofischer, USA). Calibration was done with 2ul of elution buffer from Genekam mini column.nucleic acid isolation kit. After that 2ul of isolated nucleic acid RNA or DNA were used to measure the amount twice and average amount per sample per ul was collected.

Results: Tissues stored in GTSS are continuous source of RNA and DNA for different analysis over a period of 4 years. They are stored at room temperature (21 °C) in room without any direct exposure to sun light. Once the solution is reduced, 5 to 10 ml GTSS to rest of stored tissue so that there is continue supply. Pieces of 5 to 20 grams per tissue in 10 to 20 ml GTSS at the beginning are used to provide a continuous source over long period.

House keeping genes for beta actin and beta globin in real time PCR in 14 samples are showing that there is hardly any difference between the isolations done over a period of 4 years in real time setting. (Table 1 and 2) The ten-fold dilutions during PCR analysis are indicating that isolated nucleic acid can be diluted up to 5-fold or even more.

Conventional PCR for presence of housekeeping genes in 10 samples were shown also successful bands in gel agarose and indicate the presence of RNA and DNA i.e., there were successful isolation of nucleic acids. Intensity of these bands indicate that there should be high amount of the nucleic acid in the sample.

Spectrometric studies indicate that there is variation ranging from 32 to 2 ug / ml in 14 isolated samples from human placenta and umbilical cord with mini column kits.

100 ul solution from stored issue was used to isolate the nucleic acid with mini column kit. 10 to 20 ml GTSS was added in the tissues, once solution was used, which provided a continuous source for analysis. It means that more than 100 isolations were done till today for RNA and DNA isolation from these samples.

Umbilical cord tissue provided more nucleic acid than the placenta as it was almost 5 times more.

Discussion: We are presenting a long-term storage solution for human placenta and umbilical cord as examples. These stored tissues are acting a long-term source for RNA and DNA. 100 ul of this stored tissue input for mini column isolation is sufficient to provide 50 to 100 ul eluted nucleic acid for conducting various real time and conventional PCR studies. This solution does not need any freezing as done with other studies in literature. The cost of this solution is Euro 30 for 100 ml. This solution can be stored at room temperature. Moreover, GTSS is used to store the tissues for 4 years and still it is acting as source of nucleic acid in our laboratory against the solutions mentioned in literature, which provides only for very short period ranging from a few days to a few months. (Mutter et al. 2004, Allen-Hall and McNevin 2013) except nitrogen liquid for long term storage, which is not feasible in most of laboratories around the world. (Lindner et al.) The results of this research work are indicating that this storage solution may be a suitable solution for many institutes, biobanks and other laboratories looking to store the tissue over years to conduct different analysis around the world. To our surprise, umbilical cord provides higher output of nucleic acid than that of placenta, this variation of nucleic acid needs to be studied further. We isolated more than hundred times the nucleic acid to be used in our laboratory work, but in this work, we are showing the results of a part of our experiments as an example.

Conclusion: To our knowledge, it may be a first long-term storage solution for human tissues, which are to be continued source of RNA and DNA for real time and conventional PCR analysis. The storage period is more than 4 years at room temperature.

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Table 1 showing spectrometric values of isolated RNA and DNA from different isolations after 4 years of storage time.

Sample number	Tissue	Total RNA ng/μl	Total DNA ng/μl
1	Umbilical cord	26,23	33,8
2	Umbilical cord	19,76	26,6
3	Umbilical cord	24,45	32,25
4	Umbilical cord	26,7	37,15
5	Umbilical cord	19,8	25,3
6	Umbilical cord	23,08	29,6
7	Umbilical cord	27,75	34,45
8	Umbilical cord	26,15	33,65
9	Umbilical cord	21,85	28,5
10	Umbilical cord	28,6	36
11	Placenta	1,03	1,15
12	Placenta	1,16	2,1
13	Placenta	1,43	2,2
14	Placenta	1,45	2,65

Table 2 showing the presence of RNA and DNA with real time PCR internal controls in different nucleic acid isolations.

Sample number	Tissue	RNA internal control	DNA internal control
1	Umbilical cord	++	++
2	Umbilical cord	++	++
3	Umbilical cord	++	++
4	Umbilical cord	++	++
5	Umbilical cord	++	++
6	Umbilical cord	++	++
7	Umbilical cord	++	++
8	Umbilical cord	++	++
9	Umbilical cord	++	++
10	Umbilical cord	++	++
11	Placenta	+	+
12	Placenta	+	+
13	Placenta	+	+
14	Placenta	+	+
15	negativ control	-	-